

**A Love Letter to America:
Bad Bunny Super Bowl Halftime Show—
Decolonial Political Economy of
Contradictions, Hegemonic Incorporation, and Imperial Reproduction**

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the Super Bowl Halftime Show of Bad Bunny as a cultural-political spectacle. The pop-music extravaganza negotiates authenticity and resistance of marginalized identities and commodification under the dominant media. Questions raised were the following: RQ1: What contradictions structure the spectacle? RQ2: Why are they incorporated into the hegemony? RQ3: How does incorporation reproduction imperial political economy? Hegemony, counter-hegemony, culture industry, power hierarchy, decoloniality, dissent, capture, cultural identity, and labor value guided this investigation of this specific instance of popular culture. This qualitative study utilized political economy as the umbrella framework of analysis. Findings revealed the following. Contradictions abound. The songs encode class struggle, anti-colonialism, national liberation, gender fluidity, and intersectional identity politics. Imperial *mauvaise-foi* Apollonian construct and authentic Dionysian passion fused to generate engagement and to mainstream diversity and decenter Anglophone cultural hegemony. Hispanophone performance was a counter-hegemonic act where English is the hegemonic language. This show served as an aesthetic-political ritual in which the dominant media enable and at the same time constrain cultural authenticity. Overall, it was a safe dissent for a few minutes. At the same time, the Super Bowl is in the business of making money. Emotional resonance, liberal diversity narratives, platform capitalism, and amplification of algorithms drive the popularity of Bad Bunny. Impacts were increased awareness of colonial conditions, exposure to Latin cultures, and the invigorated pride of people from Canada to South America. There are cultural, political-economic, and decolonial implications of this Super Bowl Halftime Show of Bad Bunny. Yet, pop music here functions as a field of contradictions. The performance of *Latinidad* was a counter-hegemonic affirmation expression and commodified hegemonic incorporation or absorption at the same time. Structural inequalities rooted in colonialism were exposed, though in fun, non-threatening, seemingly innocent songs and dances. Hegemonic cooptation and decolonial empowerment occurred simultaneously. At the end of the day, cultural inclusion led to the reproduction of the imperial stronghold over the political economy. There was no structural transformation. Recommendations include decolonial pedagogy, critical popular culture literacy, and policy emphasis on all-around equity.

Keywords: Authenticity, Bad Bunny, Contradictions, Decolonial Cultural Criticism and Studies, Hegemonic Cooptation, Imperial Reproduction, Political Economy, Popular Culture, Super Bowl Halftime Show

Introduction

Structural Context of the Empirical Case and Research Site

This article examines the Super Bowl LX Halftime show on February 8, 2026 in Santa Clara, California, as a U.S. imperial media apparatus. The show lasted exactly for 13 minutes and 41 seconds only. Yet, it has sparked massive reactions, both in support of and in opposition to the cultural extravaganza.

This paper focuses on the content and form of the Bad Bunny performance. Highlighted were Hispanophone songs, Puerto Rican symbolism, and gender disruption. Puerto Rico is a U.S. unincorporated territory which is in political and economic subordination to the U.S. mainland.

Problématique

Cultural visibility of colonial difference increases. However, structural relations of power remain unchanged. Decolonial expression is in tension with imperial-capitalist incorporation.

Research Gap

Because he appears not to simply provide entertainment. Rather, he seems to break the mainstream music mold with political-economy lenses. Themes include nostalgia, cultural identity, gentrification, activism, more properly, “artivism” or the use of the arts, including music and performance as tools of activism, coloniality, decoloniality, resistance, gender, and masculinities (Barreiro Leon, 2025; Figueroa, 2021; Garcia-Borbón, 2024; Gargiulo & Lugo-Vélez, 2024). Thus, academics are conducting serious research on the music of Bad Bunny for the intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1991, 2023) of his music. This paper fills the research gap by providing a causal mechanism that weaves together three components that other research publications have not. These elements are contradictions, hegemonic incorporation, and reproduction.

General Purpose

The purpose of this article is to specify the causal mechanisms that transform decolonial difference into economic value and hegemonic legitimacy.

Research Questions

In relation to the research gap above, this research asks three research questions:

RQ1: What contradictions structure the spectacle?

RQ2: Why are they incorporated into the hegemony?

RQ3: How does incorporation reproduction imperial political economy?

Critical Literature Review

Overview

This critical literature review presents seminal works that reveal antagonistic and non-antagonistic tensions which characterize the Bad Bunny spectacle. It reviewed the arguments of these key authors, their contributions, as well as their limitations (Gramsci, 1989; D. E. Hall et al., 2013; S. Hall et al., 2016, 2016, 2021, 2025; Horkheimer & Adorno, 2002; *Is the ‘Decolonial Turn’ a Colonial Return?*, 2018; W. Mignolo, 2011; W. D. Mignolo, 2007; W. Mignolo & Walsh, 2018; Nietzsche, 2024; Quijano, 2023; Rockhill, 2014, 2017a, 2017b). Due to page limits based on author guidelines, the literature review is presented in a matrix. See Table below.

Table 1 Tensions, Contributions, and Limitations

Authors	Tensions		Contributions	Limitations
Adorno	Standardization	Autonomy	Critique of culture industry	Over-determination
Bad Bunny Studies	Authentic Identity	Market	Cultural insights	No integration of political economy
Gramsci	Domination; Hegemony	Consent; Counter-Hegemony	Explain Cooptation and Dissent	Weak economic mechanism
Hall	Encoding	Decoding	Audience agency	Underplays structure
Marx	Value	Labor	Explains accumulation	Less cultural mediation
Mignolo	Epistemic Difference	Western Dominance	Decolonial lens	Limited empirical linkage
Nietzsche	Hegemonic Apollonian rational order	Counter-Hegemonic Dionysian irrational chaos	Aesthetic duality; Foundation of cultural critique	Weak structural explanation of power
Quijano	Coloniality	Modernity	Power hierarchy	No commodification mechanism

Gaps in the Literature

Several authors have contributed to understanding tensions in society. However, each contribution has its limitations. Furthermore, a synthesis gap exists, as no research explicitly integrated the gaps into a cohesive framework to study Bad Bunny. Bad Bunny researchers tend to idolize him as all-good: not this paper. This article is more nuance, digs deep into political economy, and delves into the conflicting tensions pulling and pushing Bad Bunny in both directions at the same time. This paper fills the gap. See the conceptual framework below in a Figure.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

In antiquity and early modernity, philosophers viewed society holistically from the biological, cultural, economic, linguistic, political, and social perspectives as a unified field (Aristotle, 2009; Confucius, 2000; Kautilya, 2016; Marx, 1859; Plato, 2007; Smith, 2013). Later, however, they were split into the separate fields of biology, economics, linguistics, political science, and sociology, losing sight of the wholeness of science, technology and society.

Today, political economy perspective resurges and once again unites the hitherto disparate units of politics, economics, and culture back together (Ty, 2016, 2020, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c). Culture includes a host of elements. They comprise the arts, beliefs, customs, education, language, music, objects, religion, social norms, traditions, and values (Ty et al., 2012). The political economy outlook is critical to understanding the overall situation of a given phenomenon, in this case the Bad Bunny spectacle. See Figure below.

Figure 2 Political Economy Perspective

The concepts and tensions are operationalized as well as the mechanisms and outputs described in the following theoretical framework. See Table below.

Table 2 Theoretical Framework

Political Economy	Operationalization	Tensions		Mechanisms	Outputs
RQ1: Political Contradiction	Colonial Difference	Decolonial expression	Imperial platform	Coexistence under asymmetry	Cultural tensions
RQ2: Economic Cooptation	Commodification	Cultural disruption	Commodification	Selection + formatting + branding	Market expansion
RQ3: Reproduction of the Political Economy	Imperial reproduction	Cultural transformation	Stabilization	Profit extraction + legitimacy	System persistence

Methodology

The research design of this article is qualitative, theory-driven critical bounded case study. Data collection methods include performance observation in social media, such as Facebook, TikTok, YouTube, listening to the full Halftime show music performance, media discourse, and scholarly literature. The procedure of data collection includes the identification of contradictions, tracing incorporation, and evaluation of the reproduction of the hegemonic mainstream. The analytic logic is abductive inference and theory-informed interpretation. Accuracy and consistency are based on theoretical triangulation and matching observation of the spectacle with the theories. This research is limited to interpretation only, as quantitative metrics were not utilized.

Findings

This section provided the answers to the following three research questions. RQ1: What contradictions structure the spectacle? RQ2: Why are they incorporated into the hegemony? RQ3: How does incorporation reproduction imperial political economy? Due to page limits, the answers are presented in tabular format. See Table below.

Table 3 Contradictions, Incorporation, and Reproduction

RQs	Tensions		Empirical Observation	Mechanism	Outcomes
RQ1: What: Contradictions	Spanish	English dominance	Hispanophone performance in U.S. broadcast	Linguistic disruption tolerated within format	Symbolic inclusion
	Puerto Rican identity	U.S. imperial frame	National symbols displayed	Territorial identity commodified	Cultural visibility without sovereignty
	Gender fluidity	Heteronormativity	Nonconforming aesthetics	Difference aestheticized	Market differentiation
RQ2: Why: Hegemonic Cooptation	Disruption	Profit	Diversity attracts varied and global audiences	Audience expansion logic	Revenue growth
	Inclusion	Legitimacy	Representation signals progressiveness	Brand legitimacy construction	Consent generation
RQ3: How: Reproduction	Resistance	Incorporation	Performance embedded in NFL format	Controlled integration	Neutralization of threat
	Visibility	Power	No change in ownership and governance	Structural containment	Imperial reproduction

Discussion

This article has benefited from the theoretical contributions of seed literature that investigate tensions (Gramsci, 1989; S. Hall et al., 2025; Horkheimer & Adorno, 2002; *Is the ‘Decolonial Turn’ a Colonial Return?*, 2018; Marx, 1859; Nietzsche, 2024; Quijano, 2023). Nevertheless, this article did not merely blindly apply and plug their theories deductively into this study. Rather, it has revised their work based on the findings of this research. See Table below.

Table 4 Comparison to Previous Literature

Theory	Standard Position	Revision based on Findings
Adorno	Total standardization of culture	Selective incorporation of difference
Gramsci	Consent via ideology	Consent via commodified inclusion
Hall	Audience agency	Agency without structural transformation

Theory	Standard Position	Revision based on Findings
Marx	Value extracted from labor	Value also extracted from cultural difference
Mignolo	Coloniality of knowledge; Western epistemic dominance	Decoloniality selectively appropriated and commodified within global cultural industries
Quijano	Colonial hierarchy persists	Coloniality reproduced through media commodification
Rockhill	Dissent captured	Spectacle operationalizes capture mechanism

Furthermore, presented in this section are the data interpretation, general comparison to prior literature, surprises, limitations, contributions, and implications of this study. See Table below.

Table 5 Data Interpretation

Discussion	Content
Data Interpretation	Findings reveal that cultural difference is not suppressed. It is structurally absorbed into imperial media logics. Decolonial signals were converted into consumable value.
General Comparison to Previous Literature	The findings extend Gramsci (consent), Marx (value extraction), Quijano (coloniality), Rockhill (capture). It adds to Bad Bunny literature with mechanism of tensions, incorporation, and reproduction.
Surprises or Unexpected Findings	Difference is not eliminated. Difference is intensified and used for maker expansion. Inclusion does not weaken, but strengthen, imperial legitimacy.
Limitations	Single-case design; interpretive methodology; no audience ethnography; no platform metrics.
Contributions to Theory	Unified model: Colonial Difference → Commodification → Imperial Reproduction; Unified decolonial theory + political economy + media studies.
Contributions to Practice	Reframes cultural representation debates toward structural ownership and governance.
Implications	Representation without redistribution functions as stabilizing mechanism of empire, not transformation.

Conclusion

Summary

This research investigated and answered three research questions. RQ1: Contradiction generates tension between decolonial expressions and imperial structure. RQ2:

Commodification of difference leads to hegemonic cooptation for market expansion. RQ3: Cultural inclusion leads to the reproduction and stabilization of imperial political economy, not transformation.

Recommendations

1. **Recommendation for Policy:** To move from symbolic inclusion to structural media equity and ownership.
2. **Recommendation for Practice:** Critical media literacy must include discussions away from mere commodification of cultural difference.
3. **Recommendation for Further Research:** Conduct comparative global studies on the role of mainstreaming hitherto ethnic popular cultures, such as Ana Tijoux (Chile), K-Pop (Korea), Rokia Traoré (Mali), Sean Paul (Jamaica), and Youssou N'Dour (Senegal).

Conclusion

In the final analysis, the inclusion of difference in the Super Bowl LX Halftime show was necessary for Puerto Ricans, *Latinidad*, and minorities in general but not sufficient. They felt seen. Cultural visibility was clearly an achievement. Yet, it did not transform difference into structural transformation. It only reinforces imperial reproduction of its stronghold on the political economy, what with increased market segmentation and increased profits from difference.

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